

Data Management Plan for the DACE project, version 0

Version 1

Description

The Latvian Council of Sciences Fundamental and Applied Research Programme project "Multi-material Dust Astrochemistry (DACE)" project will generate astrochemical modelling data - chemical evolution of interstellar clouds and star-forming regions. Data to be stored include macroscopical physical conditions, evolving parameters for interstellar dust grains, while the main and most voluminous output is the calculated abundances of chemical species in the gas-phase and ice mantles on the grains. A basic description for each dataset type or simulation is to be included.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Multi-material Dust
Astrochemistry (DACE),
Izp-2025/1-0065

Researchers

Juris Kalvans (0000-0002-2962-7064)

Organizations

Ventspils University College

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for the DACE project, version 0](#)

Description:

The Latvian Council of Sciences Fundamental and Applied Research Programme project "Multi-material Dust Astrochemistry (DACE)" project will generate astrochemical modelling data - chemical evolution of interstellar clouds and star-forming regions. Data to be stored include macroscopical physical conditions, evolving parameters for interstellar dust grains, while the main and most voluminous output is the calculated abundances of chemical species in the gas-phase and ice mantles on the grains. A basic description for each dataset type or simulation is to be included.

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [Multi-material Dust Astrochemistry \(DACE\), Izp-2025/1-0065](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-02-25](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP, grant DACE, dataset 1

Description for first astrophysical numerical modelling data to be generated in the initial research of multi-material dust astrochemistry.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data are calculated for evaluating the chemical effects of grains consisting of different materials, instead of a single uniform chemical compositions. It results in variations of grain temperatures and their surface adsorption properties.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Machine-readable text

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No analogous or complementary data exist as far as I know.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Astrochemistry students or scientists.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

Data information will be described in a publication.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Astronomy keywords for A&A, MNRAS, AAS journals

<https://www.aanda.org/for-authors/latex-issues/information-files#pop>

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Initial plan is to provide data upon a justified request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv/en/>

It is the Latvian national "default" science data repository.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Text editor; probably also Excel or an equivalent program.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The license is self-explaining

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2033-12-31

Up to 5 years after end of the DACE grant in 2028.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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Initial management done by project leader. If it becomes a significant work, some tasks will be delegated to project members.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Data not sensitive in any way, no measures are expected to be applied.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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